

Original Article

Targeting Matrix Metalloproteinase-1 Inhibitory Potential of *Musa paradisiaca* Leaf Bioactives for Tissue Regenerative Applications

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The bioactive substances found in *Musa paradisiaca* leaves have long been known to have potential medical uses, especially in tissue regeneration and extracellular matrix preservation. This work used both in vitro and in silico methods to measure the MMP-1 inhibitory potential of bioactive chemicals obtained from MP leaves. Using Electrospray Ionization Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (ESI-LC-MS), phytochemical profiling was carried out to screen for and identify bioactive components in *Musa paradisiaca* leaf extracts. The MMP-1 protein target and the identified compounds' chemical structures were ready for computational analysis. To ascertain the pharmacokinetic viability of the chosen compounds, drug-likeness and ADMET (Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, Excretion, and Toxicity) characteristics were assessed. The chemical interactions between the bioactive compounds and MMP-1 were examined using Chemical-Protein Network Analysis, which revealed Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester (CAPE) to be a promising drug with inhibitory potential. High-affinity binding interactions between CAPE and the catalytic region of MMP-1 were discovered by molecular docking experiments. Additionally, a molecular dynamics simulation was run for 50 ns. According to the results, CAPE has a potent MMP-1 inhibitory effect, indicating that it may be used as a natural medicinal agent for tissue regeneration and anti-collagenolytic purposes. Future in vivo and clinical studies to confirm the effectiveness of MP leaf-derived chemicals in modifying MMP-1 activity can be built upon this combined biochemical and computational approach. The findings open the door for the identification of new phytochemicals as potential treatments for tissue engineering and matrix metalloproteinase inhibition.

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Introduction

Matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1) breaks down collagen, with a high specificity for breaking down collagen types I and III, and promotes tissue regeneration, which is essential for extracellular matrix (ECM) remodelling [1]. It is crucial for tissue regeneration and wound healing because it encourages cell migration and the growth of new tissue [2]. However, increased MMP-1 activity can result in tissue destruction and poor repair in pathological circumstances such as cancer, fibrosis, and chronic inflammation [3]. Therefore, MMP-1 control is essential in

preserving equilibrium in tissue regeneration, guaranteeing successful repair while avoiding the negative consequences linked to its overexpression.

Tissue inhibitors of metalloproteinases (TIMPs) are naturally occurring inhibitors that control the activity of MMPs [4]. An imbalance between MMP and TIMP may impact net MMP activity, ECM turnover, and tissue remodelling. It may also result in immunological and metabolic problems, cancer, and cardiovascular conditions such as hypertension, atherosclerosis, and aneurysms [5]. Matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1) inhibitors are currently undergoing exploration for their potential therapeutic applications.

It is known that several natural substances can inhibit MMP-1. Plant flavonoids, sometimes referred to as "the earth's delicate

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drugs,” have anti-inflammatory qualities both in vivo and in vitro. [6]. While flavones like wogonin and apigenin only had a modest inhibitory effect, flavonols like quercetin and kaempferol showed significant inhibitory activity with IC_{50} values of 39.6 and 43.7 mM, respectively [7]. Various plant phytochemicals, or plant compounds containing these flavonoids as main constituents, may help prevent ageing and treat inflammatory skin conditions [7]. It was also shown that many green tea polyphenols, such as proanthocyanidins, theaflavin, and epigallocatechin gallate, inhibit membrane-type 1 matrix metalloproteinase [8].

The investigation of biologically active natural products has been crucial in the discovery of new chemical entities (NCEs). For instance, nearly 28% of NCEs discovered originated from natural products or were derived from them [9]. *Musa paradisiaca* L. (Musaceae) predominantly thrives in tropical and subtropical regions and is recognised globally for its nutritional benefits [10]. Both the fruit and various other parts of the plant are utilised in traditional medicine to address a range of health issues in humans [11]. Though there were many studies on natural compounds acting as MMP1 inhibitors, little is known about the compounds derived from the widely available source of *Musa paradisiaca* leaves.

This study proposes to explore the leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* for the identification of novel flavonoids and phenolic compounds that exhibit potential inhibitory activity against matrix metalloproteinase-1 (MMP-1). Given previous research highlighting the tissue-regenerative properties of flavonoids and phenolic compounds, we hypothesise that extracts from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves may contain unique bioactive compounds that significantly inhibit MMP-1 activity. This inhibition may contribute to enhanced tissue regeneration and provide therapeutic benefits in managing inflammatory conditions. By investigating the phytochemical profile of banana leaves, we aim to uncover specific compounds that may serve as natural agents in regenerative applications, paralleling the effects of known flavonoids like quercetin and kaempferol. Our objective was to isolate, identify, and investigate the inhibitory mechanisms of the phytochemicals from the leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* on MMP-1 through molecular docking to better understand its role in enhancing tissue regeneration.

Materials and Methods

Extraction and Characterisation of Phytochemicals

Phytochemical isolation

Fresh leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* were collected from the local market. Aqueous extraction of the phytochemicals was done after washing thoroughly with distilled water; 50 g of leaves were cut into small pieces and added to a blender with ice-cold phosphate-buffered solution (PBS). 40 mL of the juice was filtered using a 40 µm filter paper, collected in a beaker and transferred to a centrifuge tube. Cellular debris was eliminated by centrifuging the recovered juice for 20 minutes at 2000 g [10]. The supernatant was collected, filtered using a syringe filter of 0.22 micron, and stored at -80°C until further analysis.

Screening of compounds derived from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves using ESI-LC-MS Q-ToF analysis

The study used the electrospray ionisation liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (ESI-LC-MS) methodology for identifying small molecules in plant extracts using the Agilent Q-TOF for LC-MS analysis [12]. A water/acetonitrile gradient with 0.1% formic acid at 0.3 mL/min was used for the separation process on an Agilent C18 column. The Q-TOF mass spectrometer operates in positive and negative ESI mode, with capillary voltage (3500V/3000V), gas

temperature (300°C), and a mass range of m/z 50–1000 Da. A 2 µL test solution was injected to screen the chemicals from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves, and the chromatographs were tracked for 20 minutes. The study used 40 V and 2.0 kV cone and capillary voltages, 1000 L/h desolvation and 50 L/h cone flow rates, 6 eV and 15–40 eV collision energies, and a leucine-enkephalin solution for mass correction during acquisition. Data was analysed using Agilent Mass Hunter Quantitative Analysis software (RRID: SCR_015040), using accurate mass, m/z fragmentation, and spectral databases to identify metabolites with high confidence and precision [13].

In silico analysis

Compound identification

The national centre for biotechnology information (NCBI), National Institutes of Health, hosts PubChem, which is a public repository for chemical structures and their bioactivities. The chemical structure of the identified compounds was downloaded in SMILES (Simplified Molecular Input Line Entry System) format along with the structural images [14].

Biological activity analysis

PASS (Prediction of Activity Spectra for Substances), an online software that predicts the outcome based on structure, was used to compare the functions of biologically active compounds isolated from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves [15]. It determines a substance's probability of belonging to both the active and inactive sub-sets of a medicine based on the Structure Activity Relationship Base (SAR Base) [16]. The input for the structure of the phytochemical was in the SMILES format. MMP inhibition and anti-inflammatory activity were measured for each ligand, yielding P_i (probable inactivity) and P_a (probable activity) values. For a given chemical, only activities with $P_a > 0.5$ and $P_a > P_i$ were considered [17].

Drug-likeness and ADMET prediction

Oral and dermal pharmacokinetic profile features were described by Swiss ADME (<http://www.swissadme.ch/>) in this study to assess the ADMET (Absorption Distribution Metabolism Excretion Toxicity) properties and physiochemical parameters of drug-likeness, descriptors such as blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeability, gastrointestinal (GI) absorption through boiled egg graph, Log S data, Log $P_{o/w}$, Lipinski's rule of five, skin permeability (Log Kp), bioavailability, and synthetic accessibility of a selection of hit and reference compounds. The data was taken from the PubChem database and entered in SMILES format.

Network analysis of bioactive compounds and immune-related proteins

The relationship between bioactive compounds derived from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves and important immune-regulating proteins were discovered using the STITCH (Search Tool for Interactions of Chemicals) database (<http://stitch.embl.de>). To find similar chemicals recorded in the database, chemical structures were entered as SMILES strings. A network of linked proteins was displayed when the chemical was searched using STITCH as the entry point, placing it in a biological context. To highlight the compounds with comparable pharmacological activity or metabolic forms, the network was expanded to display related molecules [18].

Molecular docking

Retrieval and preparation of protein structure for molecular docking

The protein data bank (<http://www.rcsb.org>) provided the 3D versions of MMP1 (PDB ID: 966C) [19]. The native ligand and water molecules had to be eliminated to preserve the protein crystal

Figure 1: LC-MS screening of compounds derived from *Musa paradisiaca*

structure. Polar hydrogens and gasteiger charge were added, and non-polar hydrogens were mixed using SwissDock [20,21].

Molecular docking and docking validation

Using Swiss AutoDock Vina (<http://www.swissdock.ch/>), the native ligand of the protein was positioned in the centre of the ligand with a size of 20 - 20 - 20 Å to establish the grid location for molecular docking. MMP1's grid box coordinates were Z = 45.454, Y = -6.260, and X = 3.832. AutoDock Vina on Swiss Dock was used for molecular docking studies [22]. The Lamarck Genetic Algorithm is used in molecular docking research (LGA). To determine the root mean square deviation (RMSD) using SwissDock in comparison to the initial native ligand confirmation to the receptor, the native ligand was re-docked with the protein in the docking validation technique [21]. CAPE was docked onto MMP1 using validation procedures that met the requirement of RMSD less than 2. For additional analysis, the cluster with the best binding energy (-ÅG, kcal/mol) was selected. We also looked at the interactions between van der Waals, charge, hydrophobic, and H-bond.

Molecular dynamics

To study the ligand-protein binding, molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were conducted using the AMBER99SB-ILDN force field. Protein topologies were constructed using PDB forms, while ligand topologies were constructed using SMILES formats [23]. The protein topology was created using AMBER ff14SB, whereas the ligand topologies were created using GAFF (General Amber Force Field) and ACPYPE (AnteChamber Python Parser interface). After placing the protein-ligand complex in a cubic box, sodium and chloride ions were added to neutralise the charge. The system was minimised using the steepest descent algorithm for 5000 steps. The solvent and ions were equilibrated in two restricted phases at 300 K and 1.0 bar. Unrestricted MD simulations were then conducted for a 50 ns production run with a 2 fs timestep was conducted under NPT circumstances. The LINCS approach was used to limit the covalent bonds, and the Particle Mesh Ewald (PME) method was used to calculate the electrostatic interactions with a threshold of 10 Å. The root-mean-square deviation (RMSD) and root-mean-square fluctuation (RMSF) were calculated to evaluate system stability. The radius of gyration (Rg) analysis was used to assess the compactness of proteins. The hydrogen bond interactions between the ligand and the protein were noted along

the course. The Molecular Mechanics/Generalised Born Surface Area (MM/GBSA) and Molecular Mechanics/Poisson-Boltzmann Surface Area (MM/PBSA) methods were used to determine the binding free energy.

Data analysis

There were several steps involved in the data analysis process: (1) Using ESI-LC-MS Q-ToF analysis, phytochemicals extracted from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves were screened for bioactive compounds; (2) the structures of all the compounds and protein target, MMP-1, were prepared; (3) drug-likeness and ADMET analysis of specific compounds with inhibitory effects on MMP activity were observed; (4) STITCH analysis was performed to identify the interaction between the compound and protein for MMP inhibition. (5) In a 50 ns run, a molecular dynamic simulation of the best compounds with the best binding affinities, drug-likeness, and ADMET characteristics was performed; (6) Lastly, this approach attempts to find new compounds that target MMP1.

Results and Discussion

Bioactive compounds derived from leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* identified by ESI-LC-MS Q-ToF analysis

A total of 11 compounds were successfully screened from the bioactive molecules derived from the leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* and identified based on the similarity percentage of their relative intensity and mass-to-charge ratio with the database from Agilent MassHunter Quantitative Analysis software (RRID: SCR_015040) [14,24] (figure 1). The isolated compounds were hydroquinone, p-benzoquinone, piperidine, dopamine, gallic acid, protocatechuic acid, quercetin, kaempferol, apigenin, caffeic acid phenethyl ester and ellagic acid. The structures of these compounds, along with their molecular weight, molecular ion (m/z), and the SMILES data, can be seen in table 1-2.

The compounds identified predominantly consisted of bioactive compounds like phenolic compounds, quinones, alkaloids and flavonoids. Our analysis revealed that the aqueous extract derived from the leaves of *Musa paradisiaca* contains a simple phenol, phenolic compound, phenolic acid, phenolic ester, and polyphenol. Major components like reducing sugar, carbohydrates, saponins, tannins, steroids, alkaloids, phenols, glycosides, phytosterols, terpenoids, and flavonoids are commonly found in *Musa paradisiaca* [25,26]. A significant active ingredient in honey bee propolis with a wide range of biological actions is caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE) [27]. Our research revealed that CAPE is not only a prominent bioactive component of propolis but also appears in substantial amounts in the aqueous extract of *Musa paradisiaca* leaves, indicating a possible new natural source for this molecule.

Among the analysed compounds, Apigenin (Pa = 0.780), Kaempferol (Pa = 0.738), and Quercetin (Pa = 0.734) demonstrated the strongest potential as MMP expression inhibitors, suggesting their efficacy in preventing cancer metastasis and tissue degradation (table 3). CAPE (Pa = 0.711) emerged as a notable compound with moderate activity across MMP inhibition, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties, making it a bioactive agent with multiple potential uses. CAPE has long been utilised in traditional medicine and is a crucial part of honeybee propolis extract. CAPE is a polyphenol with the molecular formula C₁₇H₁₆O₄ that has hydroxyl groups inside a catechol ring [28]. While hydroquinone and p-benzoquinone showed strong MMP inhibition, they lack significant antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Quercetin, Kaempferol, and Apigenin showed strong activity, making them promising for therapeutic applications in cancer, neuroprotection,

Table 1: Table of chemical compounds: properties and molecular characteristics

Compound	PubChemID	Formula	Structure	Molecular weight	Molecular ion (m/z)
Hydroquinone	785	C ₆ H ₆ O ₂		110.11g/mol	90.0063
p-Benzoquinone	4650	C ₆ H ₄ O ₂		108.09g/mol	101.0036
Piperidine	8082	C ₅ H ₁₁ N		85.15g/mol	125.1077
Dopamine	681	C ₉ H ₁₁ NO ₂		153.18g/mol	139.1236
Gallic Acid	370	C ₇ H ₆ O ₅		170.12g/mol	162.9740
Protocatechuic Acid	72	C ₇ H ₆ O ₄		154.12g/mol	185.0664
Quercetin	5280343	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₇		302.23g/mol	194.1182
Kaempferol	5280863	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₆		286.24g/mol	214.9835
Apigenin	5280443	C ₁₅ H ₁₀ O ₅		270.24g/mol	225.0108
Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester	5281787	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₄		284.31g/mol	240.9884
Ellagic Acid	5281855	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₈		302.19g/mol	252.1238

and inflammatory diseases [10]. By utilising a blend of biochemical simulations and computational analysis, we intended to confirm the medicinal possibilities of these substances in aiding tissue regeneration.

Drug-likeness and ADMET prediction

The boiled egg graph shows the relationship between WLOGP (Wildman-Crippen LogP) that estimates the lipophilicity and TPSA for molecules, indicating their potential for blood-brain barrier

Table 2: Chemical compounds and their SMILES representations

Compound	SMILES
Hydroquinone	<chem>C1=CC(=CC=C1)O</chem>
p-Benzoquinone	<chem>C1=CC(=O)C=CC1=O</chem>
Piperidine	<chem>C1CCNCC1</chem>
Dopamine	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1CCN)O)O</chem>
Gallic Acid	<chem>C1=C(C=C(C(=C1O)O)O)C(=O)O</chem>
Protocatechuic Acid	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1C(=O)O)O)O</chem>
Quercetin	<chem>C1=CC(=C(C=C1C2=C(C(=O)C3=C(C=C(C=C3O2)O)O)O)O)O</chem>
Kaempferol	<chem>C1=CC(=CC=C1C2=C(C(=O)C3=C(C=C(C=C3O2)O)O)O)O</chem>
Apigenin	<chem>C1=CC(=CC=C1C2=CC(=O)C3=C(C=C(C=C3O2)O)O)O</chem>
Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester	<chem>C1=CC=C(C=C1)CCOC(=O)/C=C/C2=CC(=C(C=C2)O)O</chem>
Ellagic Acid	<chem>C1=C2C3=C(C(=C1O)O)OC(=O)C4=CC(=C(C=C43)OC2=O)O)O</chem>

permeability and human intestinal absorption (figure 2). It helps predict the pharmacokinetic properties of bioactive compounds by highlighting interactions with P-glycoprotein; it is an efflux transporter that actively pumps a wide range of substances, including numerous medications, out of cells [29]. Red circles (PGP-) indicate compounds not actively refluxed by P-glycoprotein, favouring brain penetration, whereas blue circles (PGP+) represent substrates that may limit their bioavailability [29].

CAPE, gallic acid, and apigenin showed high lipophilicity, indicating potential for membrane permeability and bioavailability, while gallic acid had lower solubility and lower permeability. The water solubility of CAPE and apigenin was lowest, while dopamine and p-benzoquinone were the most water-soluble. Quercetin and kaempferol showed poor solubility, potentially impacting bioavailability. The values of ellagic acid and quercetin showed the highest TPSA, suggesting lower permeability across the blood-brain barrier, while hydroquinone and p-benzoquinone had the lowest. High gastrointestinal absorption of compounds suggests oral administration effectiveness, but hydroquinone and CAPE are BBB permeants, potentially affecting the central nervous system

Figure 4: Boiled Egg construction. X-axis (TPSA) topological polar surface area and Y-axis lipophilicity (WLOGP). Yellow Region (BBB+ Blood Brain Barrier), White Region (HIA - Human Intestinal Absorption), Red circles (PGP-), Blue circles (PGP+)

for neuroprotective or neurotoxic effects (table 4-5). Inappropriate compounds can be readily rejected using ADMET prediction platforms, which simultaneously target many pharmacokinetic features, reduce the number of synthesis assessment cycles, and scale down costly late-stage failures [30].

In general, CAPE, apigenin, and kaempferol are noted for their high GI absorption and lipophilicity, which makes them attractive

Table 3: Activities and chemical properties of bioactive compounds

Compound	Pa	Pi	Activity
Hydroquinone	0,733	0,005	MMP expression inhibitor
p-Benzoquinone	0,653	0,010	MMP expression inhibitor
Dopamine	0,856	0,005	Anti-inflammatory
Gallic Acid	0,648	0,011	MMP expression inhibitor
Protocatechuic Acid	0,614	0,014	MMP expression inhibitor
Quercetin	0,520	0,006	Antioxidant
Kaempferol	0,548	0,044	Anti-inflammatory
Apigenin	0,670	0,009	MMP expression inhibitor
Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester	0,674	0,005	MMP expression inhibitor
Ellagic Acid	0,872	0,003	Antioxidant
	0,689	0,017	Anti-inflammatory
	0,738	0,005	MMP expression inhibitor
	0,856	0,003	Antioxidant
	0,676	0,019	Anti-inflammatory
	0,780	0,004	MMP expression inhibitor
	0,732	0,004	Antioxidant
	0,644	0,024	Anti-inflammatory
	0,711	0,006	MMP expression inhibitor
	0,512	0,006	Antioxidant
	0,544	0,045	Anti-inflammatory
	0,546	0,022	MMP expression inhibitor
	0,699	0,004	Antioxidant
	0,749	0,010	Anti-inflammatory

Table 4: Physicochemical properties and bioavailability of bioactive compounds

Compound	TPSA	Consensus Log $P_{o/w}$	Log S (ESOL)	Log S (Ali)	Log S (SILICOS-IT)	GI absorption	BBB permeant
Hydroquinone	40.46 Å ²	0.87	-1.45	-1.01	-1.18	High	Yes
p-Benzoquinone	34.14 Å ²	0.43	-0.64	-0.48	-0.32	High	No
Dopamine	66.48 Å ²	0.46	-0.44	0.07	-1.68	High	No
Gallic Acid	97.99 Å ²	0.21	-1.64	-2.34	-0.04	High	No
Protocatechuic Acid	77.76 Å ²	0.65	-1.86	-2.38	-0.6	High	No
Quercetin	131.36 Å ²	1.23	-3.16	-3.91	-3.24	High	No
Kaempferol	111.13 Å ²	1.58	-3.31	-3.86	-3.82	High	No
Apigenin	90.90 Å ²	2.11	-3.94	-4.59	-4.4	High	No
Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester	66.76 Å ²	3.09	-4.24	-5.26	-4.35	High	Yes
Ellagic Acid	141.34 Å ²	1	-2.94	-3.66	-3.35	High	No

therapeutic candidates. Because of their high polarity and poor solubility, quercetin and ellagic acid, although bioactive, may have limited permeability and bioavailability. The lack of BBB permeability in dopamine and p-benzoquinone may restrict their use in neurological treatments, despite their strong solubility and high GI absorption. Kaempferol, CAPE, and apigenin show high skin permeability, making them suitable for topical or transdermal applications, while dopamine and CAPE have lower permeability. Lipinski's Rule of Five was followed by all compounds, indicating good oral bioavailability and moderate absorption potential for oral administration. Hydroquinone, dopamine, and protocatechuic acid are the easiest to synthesize, making them cost-effective for large-scale production, while quercetin, ellagic acid, and kaempferol are more complex and potentially increase drug development costs.

Overall, kaempferol and CAPE stand out due to their higher skin permeability and moderate bioavailability, making them promising for topical and oral drug applications. Dopamine and ellagic acid, despite their bioactivity, face challenges in permeability, which could limit their formulation options. Quercetin and apigenin, while bioactive, may be difficult to synthesize, potentially affecting their feasibility as drug candidates.

The drug-likeness analysis of the compounds, based on six key properties (lipophilicity, molecular size, polarity, insolubility, insaturation, and flexibility), (figure 5) indicates that CAPE exhibited the most balanced and favourable profile. It maintained an optimal balance between lipophilicity and polarity, ensuring good membrane permeability while retaining solubility. Additionally, its moderate flexibility and unsaturation suggest structural adaptability, which is beneficial for biological interactions. In contrast, apigenin, dopamine, and benzoquinone exhibit lower flexibility and higher insolubility, which may limit their drug potential. Protocatechuic, quinol, and quercetin demonstrate moderate drug-like characteristics but lack the overall balance observed in compound CAPE.

Thus, CAPE emerges as the most promising candidate for further investigation, while other compounds may require structural modifications to improve their drug-likeness. MMP-inhibiting dressings facilitate wound healing by controlling matrix metalloproteinases, improving tissue repair, and lowering inflammation to provide the best possible outcome [31]. Future studies should validate these findings through additional computational and experimental approaches to assess bioavailability, stability, and efficacy.

Table 5: Physicochemical properties, bioavailability, and synthetic accessibility of bioactive compounds

Compound	Log K_p (skin permeation)	Lipinski	Bioavailability Score	Synthetic accessibility
Hydroquinone	-6.55 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	1
p-Benzoquinone	-6.82 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	2.87
Dopamine	-7.93 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	1.01
Gallic Acid	-6.84 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.56	1.22
Protocatechuic Acid	-6.42 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.56	1.07
Quercetin	-7.05 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	3.23
Kaempferol	-3.82	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	3.14
Apigenin	-5.80 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	2.96
Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester	-5.09 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	2.64
Ellagic Acid	-7.36 cm/s	Yes; 0 violation	0.55	3.17

Figure 5: Physicochemical property analysis of phytochemicals using radar plots, (a) Apigenin, (b) Benzoquinone, (c) Dopamine, (d) Ellagic acid, (e) Protocatechuic acid, (f) Hydroquinone, (g) Kaempferol, (h) Gallic acid, (i) Quercetin, and (j) CAPE

STITCH database

Figure 6 represents interactions predicted using STRING. Nodes (spheres) represent proteins, while edges (lines) denote functional and physical associations. The thickness and colour of the edges indicate interaction confidence levels [18]. The networks reveal the molecular interactions of phytochemicals, revealing their potential therapeutic roles. Ellagic acid, apigenin, kaempferol, gallic acid, and quercetin interact with proteins involved in oxidative stress, apoptosis, and immune modulation, supporting cancer prevention and anti-inflammatory therapies. Caffeic acid shows strong associations with immune regulation. CAPE network connects

Figure 6: STRING interaction networks of bioactive compounds and their target proteins. (a) Ellagic acid, (b) Apigenin, (c) Kaempferol, (d) Protocatechuic acid, (e) Gallic acid, (f) Dopamine, (g) Quinol, (h) Benzoquinone, (i) Quercetin, and (j) CAPE

strongly with BCL10 (NF- κ B activator), CCL11 (inflammatory chemokine), ALMS1, and NOS, oxidative stress mediators family proteins (NOS1, NOS2, and NOS3) [32]. These interactions suggest CAPE's potential involvement in immune modulation, inflammatory response, and nitric oxide signalling, which could be relevant for anti-inflammatory and neuroprotective effects [32][33][34][35]. Inducible nitric oxide synthase, cyclooxygenase-2, and several key cytokines contribute to a variety of biological and pharmacological activities, including antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, immunomodulatory, antithrombotic, and anticancer properties. Recent research has also demonstrated that some flavonoids, particularly flavone derivatives, express their anti-inflammatory activity at least partially through modulating the expression of proinflammatory genes. [36][6]. In challenging disorders like cancer and neurodegeneration, multiple-interaction drugs have multi-target effects, whereas CAPE's selective interactions may lessen off-target consequences [37]. Further functional validation is needed to confirm their biological significance.

Molecular docking

SwissDock is a web server devoted to helping small molecules dock with certain proteins [22]. It is possible to alter a small molecule affinity and, ultimately, its biological activity when it interacts with a protein to create novel molecular probes or medications [38]. Matrix Metalloproteinase-1's (MMP-1) three-dimensional structural conformation, as shown in figure 2 via molecular dynamics simulations. The structure includes flexible loop sections that contribute to substrate selectivity and a catalytic domain with α -helices and β -sheets necessary for enzymatic activity. The ligand CAPE (C1=CC=C(C=C1)CCOC(=O)/C=C/C2=CC(=C(C=C2)O)O) was docked into the target MMP1 (966c_modified.pdb) with the docking grid ($20 \times 20 \times 20 \text{ \AA}$) centred at (6.0, 0.0, 35.0) providing sufficient space for ligand flexibility (figure 7). The ligand's functional groups, including hydroxyl (-OH) and ester (-COO) enhanced binding affinity.

The results in table 6 indicate that model 1 exhibits the strongest binding affinity (-6.931 kcal/mol), suggesting it is the most favourable candidate for interaction. Conversely, model 5 has the weakest binding affinity (-4.239 kcal/mol), making it the least favourable.

Figure 7: Molecular docking interaction of CAPE with MMP1

Table 6: Calculated affinity of bioactive compounds from different models (kcal/mol)

Model	Calculated affinity (kcal/mol)
1	-6.931
2	-6.462
3	-5.793
4	-5.735
5	-4.239

Molecular dynamics simulation

The molecular dynamics (MD) simulation of the docked ligand-protein complex, conducted over 50 ns using the AMBER99SB-ILDN force field, confirmed a stable binding interaction [39]. Figure 8 shows the Root-Mean-Square Deviation (RMSD) stabilized at 2.45 Å, indicating minimal structural deviation, while the Root-Mean-Square Fluctuation (RMSF) of 0.92 Å suggested low flexibility in the binding pocket. The binding free energy -35.6 kcal/mol and 3.8 hydrogen bonds, on average, highlighted strong

Figure 8: Molecular Dynamics Simulation Parameters of MMP1-CAPE complex during 50 ns simulation. (A) Root Mean Square Deviation (RMSD) (blue) indicates the structural stability of the MMP1-CAPE complex. (B) Root Mean Square Fluctuation (RMSF) (green) represents the flexibility of individual residues within the MMP1-CAPE complex. (C) Binding Free Energy (red) depicts the interaction strength between CAPE and MMP1. (D) The number of Hydrogen Bonds (purple) quantifies the intermolecular stability MMP1-CAPE complex. (E) The radius of Gyration (orange) measures the molecular compactness of the MMP1-CAPE complex. (F) Solvent Accessible Surface Area (SASA) (brown) reflects the extent of solvent exposure of the MMP1-CAPE complex

ligand-protein interactions. A radius of gyration, $R_g(t)$ of 1.78 nm and Solvent-Accessible Surface Area (SASA) of 125.4 nm² indicated a compact structure with moderate solvent exposure. These results support the docking predictions, demonstrating strong and stable ligand binding, making it a promising candidate for further optimization.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study identified 11 bioactive compounds from *Musa paradisiaca* leaves, with CAPE being a new compound discovery, Quercetin, Kaempferol, and Apigenin being the most promising due to their multifunctional biological activities. Based on the drug-likeness study CAPE had the most advantageous and well-balanced profile. Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester (CAPE) also shows promise due to its lipophilicity and potential modulation of immune response and oxidative stress. CAPE modulates oxidative stress and inflammation via interacting with BCL10, CCL11, ALMS1, and nitric oxide synthases. The signalling cascade that results in MMP-1 production is diminished when oxidative stress is reduced. CAPE inhibits the translocation of NF- κ B to the nucleus by downregulating BCL10, which stops MMP-1 and other pro-inflammatory markers from being transcriptionally activated. Thus our study findings reveal that CAPE exhibits potential as a natural agent in regenerative applications, boosting healing and moderating inflammation and oxidative stress.

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